

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' INTEREST FOR MUSIC THROUGH INSTRUMENTAL PERFORMING ARTS IN GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract: In this article, the scientific and pedagogical features of the development of interest in music culture and art of music of general secondary school students through the performance of musical instruments are discussed.

Key words: Music art, musical performance, musical ability, skill, educational system, children's musical instruments.

In music culture classes, melodies performed on musical instruments are of great importance in developing and improving students' interest in music. It is important to teach the students to analyze the content and character of the melody from the first lessons, then they will consciously understand and perceive the content of various musical works and form their passion for music.

The correct organization of children's musical instrument performance in music culture classes has a positive effect on the formation of students' musical interests and the development of their musical feelings through it. In particular, the characteristic features of the tunes, which are performed in general, ensure that the tune, music, performance skills have a complex effect on a person. Melody and its musical expression affect human emotions, senses and consciousness. So, the influence of musical works is complex and powerful. In addition, high-quality performance of music is also very important.

The piece to be performed, the melody to be listened to, its melodic and intonational expression, artistic form, finally, is an amalgamation of music and good performance. Which of these elements has the strongest impact on students' emotions and minds? - question cannot be answered. Therefore, in our opinion, emotional and spiritual impact can be achieved only with the combination of these elements.

Although the structural elements of the melody affect different areas of the student's personality: consciousness, will, intuition, musical perception, the accompaniment of the music is perceived as a whole. This multifaceted complex effect is realized as a single process. It is also stronger than the effect of the music being played. Playing musical instruments in music culture classes is the most popular and interesting among students compared to other activities.

We conducted a questionnaire among students in the process of conducting an experiment - testing. Before the lesson begins, ask yourself, "What kind of music activity do you like best?" We distributed a questionnaire with a question.

After the lesson, we collected these questionnaires from the students. As a result, playing on children's musical instruments was recorded as a favorite type of musical activity. This is a proof of the widespread popularity of musical instrument performance among students.

Most of the power of art and the character of its influence on young learners is determined by the provard result of each of these elements and their sequence, and this unity creates a holistic effect on the person who perceives the melody and song. . From this, it can be understood that it is necessary to consider each element and determine the main aspects of influencing the students.

The most important element of the art of performing a musical piece is its emotional core. The melody reflects the ideological, educational and emotional content of the song in the form of unique melodic sounds.

It is not correct to include the work in the framework of certain, permanent, uniform requirements. Therefore, a melody can have various types of harmony, style, expressiveness, and means of expression.

Melodies not only evoke happy, lyrical, uplifting emotions. It also causes sadness and anger. In other words, the song and melody create not only positive moods, but also negative ones. All this depends on the content of the song, which reflects different aspects of life - joy, anxiety, hope, separation, etc. Now we will try to shed light on the problems of organizing music reception, which is considered the main factor in the development of students' enthusiasm for the art of music.

Music as art is a form of social consciousness. It is a reflection of life reality and times, as well as expressing a person's feelings. The main factors of the music lesson process include: enjoying listening to music, playing songs, understanding the features of music literacy, dancing and performing rhythmic movements to music, understanding the purpose of clapping and playing musical instruments: performance in order to accompany the music being taught, in order to achieve the above goal of the music lesson, the students should be interested in music first. To fulfill the tasks of musical education, it is necessary to teach students to listen. Most people don't listen to serious music because they don't understand it. And for understanding, preparation is required. Without preparation, there is no knowledge. Teaching listening is more complicated than playing a song.

It is necessary to introduce students to the high artistry of music. Such works broaden students' outlook and develop musical taste. In order to prepare a large number of literate listeners, musicians should be taught to understand and love music from childhood. Loving music means listening to music all the time. Understanding music means feeling, analyzing, knowing.

The teacher should tell the students what to pay attention to during the performance of the work. The teacher should lead during the listening. The most important thing is that the piece being listened to should be suitable for the age of the students and memorable.

Tasks set before the teacher in playing a musical instrument: arousing enthusiasm for the art of music, interest in playing a musical instrument through practical means, strengthening the musical need in children, collecting artistic impressions in students . (question - answer, through conversations).

for this:

- ☐ Simple musical pedagogical analysis of the piece to be performed.
- ☐ To use simple musical terms and terms in performance.
- ☐ Teaching to clap and sing according to the simple structure of the melody, its means of expression according to the rhythmic structures.
- ☐ Introduction to music creators, types of performers, musical instruments.

- ☒ Also know musical genres. (dance, ballet, opera, etc.).
- ☒ Knowing the structure of the work. (band, two-part or three-part).
- ☒ To know the life and works of composers.
- ☒ Know the elements of musical speech. (character, tempo, dynamics, means of musical expression).
- ☒ Knowledge of musical aesthetic information.

Students should know that music has content and that it reflects people's lives. They should also know that there is form in music (content is expression or description, form depends on the composer to express the essence of the work).

The problems of organizing the creative process in music, to increase the interest of students in the music culture lesson, to increase the efficiency of the lesson, to organize the lessons correctly, taking into account the age characteristics of the students, is the demand of the time. Theoretical analysis of the process of music education, learning the experiences of advanced teachers, dividing the lesson into different stages gives positive results.

1. Adapting students to the lesson, creating friendly relations, introducing them to the work to be done, setting individual and team tasks.
2. Strengthening the knowledge and skills of students. In this way, it is possible to expand the scope of knowledge, to develop the skills of creative approach to the subject, and to improve the activity of thinking ability so that students can think independently. In this process, students' perceptive abilities are checked.

It is necessary to pay attention to quickly attracting students to music lessons and forming signs of adaptation to this lesson. For this:

In the beginning of the lesson, it is recommended to play some cheerful, cheerful, attractive piece of music. This music, listened to in the lesson, creates an upbeat mood in the students. The most important thing is that it helps the lesson to be high-quality and interesting. It is important for the teacher to study the level of knowledge of the students and compare it with the previous ones. Along with thinking, musical creativity develops emotional activity and quick decision-making skills. This creativity of students is related to their independent activity. In music culture classes, students' creativity is mainly manifested in learning and interest in musical practice.

Preparation for creative activity is observed in 3 directions.

1. Enriching life with musical impressions. For example: creating a rhythmic, introductory part to the work (the studied song works can be given an introduction, which focuses on the development of creative movement skills).
2. Before that, the teacher will show, then in cooperation, the analysis of the song and the goal-oriented performance plan will be told. This is explained by well-known songs. It is of great importance to prepare students for creative activities through works that depend on the expression of the same and different tones, different musical images and musical characters. For example: in order to create variants of melodies, the student needs to understand the pronunciation, rhythmic experience and the existence of tones (the text of a poem, the rhythmic structure of music).

Studying, analyzing and effectively applying musical works to the educational process related to the psychological and physiological characteristics of students and their age characteristics in music culture lessons, improving the quality and effectiveness of music culture lessons,

improving the musical feelings of students. has a positive effect on development and improvement. This requires proper organization of musical culture lesson activities.

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